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A GENERAL OVERVIEW OF INCLUSIVE GROWTH: AN ANALYSIS OF ARTICLES PUBLISHED IN THE WEB OF SCIENCE (WoS) USING BIBLIOMETRIC METHODS¹

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ABSTRACT

The relationship between the approach of solving problems such as income inequality, poverty, and regional disparities solely through economic growth and reality has increased the importance of the concept of inclusive growth. The aim of this study is to analyse studies on inclusive growth using bibliometric indicators. The bibliometric analysis technique, one of the quantitative research methods, was used in this study. The studies scanned in this context consist of studies on inclusive growth written in English and included in the Web of Science database. At this point, the 626 articles identified were analysed in Biblioshiny, a web interface of the open source "R" programme. The primary findings of the study indicate that the historical process of studies in this field spans from 1992 to 2026. Findings regarding studies and authors on inclusive growth revealed that there are 2,746 authors in the field, the average age of articles is 5.17, articles written in the field have an average of 40.45 citations, and the field has an annual growth rate of 4.85%. It was also determined that there are 4.35 co-authors per study and 29.49% of articles are produced through international collaboration. In the section where the findings obtained from the analysis are examined according to publications, institutions, countries, and authors, those who contribute most to the field have been identified, and the findings are supported by numerical data. The section containing the study's findings on concepts showed that the concepts of growth, impact, management, sustainability, and sustainable development were predominantly used. Findings related to these concepts, which are predominantly used in studies on inclusive growth, were identified through word tree, word cloud, trending topics, and thematic map analyses. In the conclusion section of the study, the findings are evaluated and recommendations are made for future studies.

KEYWORDS: Inclusive Growth, Bibliometric Analysis, Biblioshiny, Web of Science (WoS).

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1. INTRODUCTION

Economic growth is an important indicator that influences the determination of a country's level of development. However, a country's economic growth alone, i.e. an increase in its national income, is not sufficient to make it developed. This situation can be associated with unsustainable, long-term and wide-ranging policy uncertainties (Rahman & Alam, 2021, p.1). This is because the people living in a country have social needs as well as economic needs. In addition, eliminating inequalities and the fair distribution of income and development among regions are equally important. Therefore, economic growth must be approached by taking into account many factors, such as political, economic, and demographic factors. In other words, growth should not only be related to the increase in total output in economic terms. Economic growth should encompass fundamental transformation, from the sectoral structure of that economy to its demographic and geographical structure, and its social and institutional structure (Acemoğlu, 2012, pp. 545-546). Therefore, economic development should not be viewed in a one-dimensional manner. The multidimensionality of this approach reveals its inclusiveness. Given that economic growth is important but not sufficient for improving welfare, inclusive growth is economic growth that provides social benefits, eliminates inequalities, highlights the dimensions of social welfare such as health, education, social relations and institutions, and ensures a relatively fair distribution of benefits (Boarini, et al, 2015, p.5). Another approach states that inclusive growth aims to achieve economic growth by raising individuals' living standards and reassessing who participates in the economy and how (Dua, et al, 2021, p.5). Therefore, economic growth can be summarised as defined by the OECD: "Inclusive growth is an economic growth that creates opportunity for all segments of the population and distributes the dividends of increased prosperity, both in monetary and non-monetary terms, fairly across society" (OECD, 2017).

The aim of this study is to examine studies on inclusive growth using bibliometric analysis methods. The study, conducted using this method, reveals a research area that can be classified as inclusive growth. In addition, it provides a graphical mapping of the concept analyses of articles written on inclusive growth. The findings from the analyses conducted in the study, which include the journals with the highest number of citations in the field of inclusive growth, the countries with the most studies, the journals with the most publications, scientific

collaborations between countries, the concepts that feature heavily in the studies, the concepts that are frequently associated, and findings on niche themes that guide new studies, enabling a more detailed assessment of the topic of inclusive growth. The findings obtained from the study are considered to be of a guiding nature for future studies, researchers, and policy makers.

2. METHODOLOGY

Bibliometric analysis is a method used to examine and analyse large amounts of scientific data. Frequently encountered in recent studies, this method allows for the emergence of nuances in a specific field and sheds light on new studies in the relevant literature. This enables researchers to gain insight into various aspects such as emerging trends in article and journal performance within their field, collaboration models, and the intellectual structure of a specific area within the existing literature (Donthu, et al, 2021, p.285). Consequently, this method has been employed to help individuals working in a particular field explore their area of study at the point of decision-making. More broadly, the bibliometric analysis method is also defined as "a part of scientific measurement science that uses mathematical and statistical methods to analyse scientific activities in a research field" (Callon, Courtial, & Laville, 1991; Aparicioi et al, 2019). The findings obtained as a result of bibliometric analyses provide a general picture of a research field that can be classified in terms of articles, authors, and journals, as well as a graphical mapping of science (Merigo & Yang, 2017; Noyons, et al, 1999). Therefore, the bibliometric analysis method is one of the quantitative methods that uses different techniques to evaluate popular research topics in a field (Aski et al., 2020, p.106). In this study, the bibliometric analysis method, one of the quantitative research techniques, was used to make findings regarding studies on inclusive growth.

Studies conducted using bibliometric analysis utilise numerous databases. The data sets contained in these databases vary depending on the database in which the research is conducted. For example, the data set for a study conducted in the Scopus database consists of studies contained in the Scopus database. In studies where bibliometric analysis is used as a method, databases such as Scopus, Web of Science (WoS), MEDLINE, PubMed, and Google Scholar are seen to be the most preferred databases (Bayar & Yaşar Uğurlu, p.1867-1868). In this study, which focuses on inclusive growth, the Web of Science (WoS) database was used as the database because it

has the largest volume among the databases (Clarivate, 2025). Therefore, the research universe is the Web of Science database. The main factor in determining this database as the research universe is that it contains a relatively large amount of research data in the social sciences (Li, et al, 2017, p.2). The sample of the research consists of studies on inclusive growth in the Web of Science (WoS) database, which was determined as the research universe. A search was conducted on 16 January 2026 using the term "inclusive growth" on this sample. The search filtered

articles that were open access and written in English. These filters can be explained by the selection of English as the universal language of science and the selection of open access articles for accessibility. It should also be noted that the analysis programme used can only analyse one language at a time. The criteria used to determine the sample for the research are shown in Figure 1 below. The filtering resulted in a dataset of 626 articles. This dataset was analysed using Biblioshiny, a web interface of the R programme.

Figure 1: Web of Science (Wos) Search Criteria.

3. FINDINGS

The components included in the dataset analysed in this study, which examines studies on inclusive growth using bibliometric analysis methods, are presented in Table 1 below. Descriptive analyses are important for understanding the dynamics of a research field. The annual number of publications in a field serves as a fundamental bibliometric measure that provides access to important information about the growth rate, productivity, and impact of research

(Hassan & Duarte, 2024, p. 2).

As is well known, descriptive analyses include information such as the number of articles in a dataset, the time span of the articles, the annual growth rate in the field, the total number of authors, the number of citations for studies, journals and authors, and the countries and universities that contribute most to the field. The descriptive analysis in Table 1 provides an overview of the dataset used in this study.

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis.

Descriptive Analysis	
Time Period	1992-2026
Number of Authors	2746
Percentage of International Author Collaboration	40.47
Sources (journals, books, etc.)	435
Average Citations per Article	22.47
Number of Studies	986
Co-authors per article	4.72
Number of Single-Authored Studies	72
Average Age of Articles	2.66
Growth Rate in the Field (Annual) %	44.62

As shown in the descriptive analysis in Table 1, studies on inclusive growth first began in 1992. The literature, which includes 986 articles in the field, has

a growth rate of 44.62%. This increase in the growth rate indicates the intensity of work in the field. Articles on inclusive growth were authored by 2,746

authors, with 40.47% of the studies based on international author collaboration. This statistical data shows how suitable the field of inclusive growth is for collaboration between authors from different countries. Furthermore, the average number of co-authors per article (4.72) also indicates the suitability of the field for collaborative work. In addition, as

noted in the descriptive analysis, the average number of citations for articles on inclusive growth is 22.47, while the average age of the articles is 2.66. This outlook of studies on inclusive growth also affects the number of annual increases in studies. Accordingly, the outlook for the annual increase in studies on inclusive growth is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Annual Publication Increase.

As seen in Figure 2, the first study on inclusive growth was conducted in 1992, and the number of studies generally shows an upward trend. The significant increase in the number of studies that began in 2013 and continued thereafter can be attributed to the economic crises around the world. Furthermore, 2025 is seen to have the highest number of studies. The break and downward trend in 2026 is due to the short period of time that has elapsed so far this year. In summary, this graph shows that the literature on inclusive growth, which began with the first study in 1992, is generally on an upward trend

and is a large field.

3.1. Publication-University-Journal Relationship

Under this heading, observations will be made regarding articles on inclusive growth in terms of universities, journals, citations, and international collaboration. Numerical data on universities publishing on inclusive growth are presented in Table 2 below. This table identifies the leading institutions in the field of inclusive growth.

Table 2: Universities With the Most Publications.

Universities	Number of Publications
TAMIL NADU AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY	23
University of Johannesburg	14
University of KwaZulu-Natal	14
University of Sydney	13
University of Toronto	12
University of Washington	12
ALL INDIA INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES	11
University of Arizona	11
UNIVERSITY OF BOSTON	10
New York University Abu Dhabi	10

Table 2 examines the universities that have published the most on inclusive growth, along with their publication counts. The top 10 institutions, ranked according to the findings, are listed in order of publication count. Accordingly, the university

with the most articles on inclusive growth is Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, with 23 articles. This is followed by the University of Johannesburg and the University of Kwazulu Natal with 14 articles each, the University of Sydney with 13 articles, the

University of Toronto and the University of Washington with 12 articles each, the All-India Institute of Medical Sciences and the University of Arizona with 11 articles each, and Boston University and New York University Abu Dhabi with 10 articles

each.

The numerical data for journals publishing articles on inclusive growth, based on the articles they published, are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Journals With the Most Publications.

Journals	Number of Publications
SUSTAINABILITY	23
DISCOVER SUSTAINABILITY	16
Journal of Cleaner Production	8
RENEWABLE & SUSTAINABLE ENERGY REVIEWS	8
Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability	5
Sustainable Development	5
ADMINISTRATIVE SCIENCES	4
CANCERS	4
COGENT ECONOMICS & FINANCE	4
COGENT SOCIAL SCIENCES	4

As shown in Table 3, the journals with the most articles are listed according to the number of publications. Sustainability magazine ranks first on the list of 10 journals in this field, with 23 articles published. Discover Sustainability magazine follows with 16 articles published. The Journal of Cleaner Production and Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews have published 8 articles each, followed by Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability

and Sustainable Development with 5 articles each. The other journals at the bottom of the list, Administrative Sciences, Cancers, Cogent Economics & Finance, and Cogent Social Sciences, have 4 articles each.

The numerical data on citations for journals that have published articles on inclusive growth are presented in Table 4, which is based on the number of citations.

Table 4: Journals With the Most Citations.

Journals	Number of Citations
SUSTAINABILITY	558
RENEWABLE & SUSTAINABLE ENERGY REVIEWS	608
Journal of Cleaner Production	548
Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability	265
International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	99
International Journal of Molecular Sciences	109
CANCERS	44
COGENT SOCIAL SCIENCES	26
DISCOVER SUSTAINABILITY	34
ENERGIES	27

Table 4 shows the citation counts of journals in which studies on inclusive growth have been published. According to this, the journal with the most citations in the field is Sustainability with 558 citations.

This is followed by Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews with 608 citations, Journal of Cleaner Production with 548 citations, Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability with 265 citations, International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health with 99 citations, International Journal of Molecular Sciences with 109 citations, Cancers with 44 citations, Cogent Social Sciences with 26 citations, Discover Sustainability with 34 citations, and Energies with 27 citations.

3.2. Geographical Analysis: Country-Publication-Citation Relationship

Geographical analysis includes findings on which countries the articles published on inclusive growth belong to, the number of articles per country, the number of citations per country, etc.

This analysis also provides findings on whether articles in the field of inclusive growth are produced through international collaboration.

Ultimately, the geographical analysis presents conclusions regarding the countries that stand out in the field of inclusive growth.

At this point, the numerical data on countries and their number of articles are presented in Table 5

below.

Table 5: Number Of Publications by Country.

Countries	Number of Articles
USA	118
INDIA	73
CHINA	49
UNITED KINGDOM	39
SOUTH AFRICA	32
AUSTRALIA	27
CANADA	26
ITALY	21
MALAYSIA	21
SPAIN	16

As can be seen in Table 5, the country with the highest number of articles is the USA, with 118 articles. This is followed by India with 73 articles, China with 49 articles, the United Kingdom with 39 articles, South Africa with 32 articles, Australia with 27 articles, Canada with 26 articles, Italy and

Malaysia with 21 articles each, and Spain with 16 articles. This list provides an overview of the countries of origin of publications on inclusive growth.

Country data on citations for articles published on inclusive growth are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Number Of Citations by Country.

Countries	Number of Citations
USA	8885
UNITED KINGDOM	2584
INDIA	1497
CANADA	1257
AUSTRALIA	1080
CHINA	1045
GERMANY	933
ITALY	912
POLAND	880
DENMARK	874

The numerical data on country-citation relationships in Table 6 shows that the USA is the leading country with 8,885 citations. This is followed by the United Kingdom with 2,584 citations, India with 1,497, Canada with 1,257, Australia with 1,080, China with 1,045, Germany with 933, Italy with 912,

Poland with 880, and Denmark with 874 citations, completing the list.

The numerical data on the contributions made by countries to the field through their work on inclusive growth are presented in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Countries' Contribution to the Field.

Countries	Freq
USA	495
INDIA	289
CHINA	186
UK	184
AUSTRALIA	112
South Africa	110
CANADA	106
ITALY	83
MALAYSIA	75
SPAIN	67

According to the numerical data on country-interaction status in Table 7, the USA ranks first with Freq=495. This is followed by India with Freq=289, China with Freq=186, the United Kingdom with Freq=184, Australia with Freq=112, South Africa

with Freq=110, Canada with Freq=106, Italy with Freq=83, Malaysia with Freq=75, and Spain with Freq=67. The contributions made by countries to the field were evaluated based on their work in the area of inclusive growth.

about them. These findings show that the process, which began in the early stages with the concepts of expression and growth factor, has recently seen concepts such as policy, poverty, climate change, artificial intelligence, sustainability, and innovation come to the fore. The realisation that economic growth alone is not sufficient for a country's development, and that inclusive growth is needed to solve problems such as poverty, unemployment, and

income inequality, has influenced the evolution of concepts. In addition, factors such as the effects of climate change and developments in technology are among the reasons for thematic shifts. Consequently, these thematic shifts are reflected in studies on inclusive growth. Finally, in this section, which analyses the concepts, a thematic map analysis was conducted. This analysis shows the clustering of articles written on inclusive growth.

Figure 7: Thematic Map Analysis.

Figure 7 shows the results of the thematic analysis of articles published on inclusive growth. The findings obtained in this analysis are examined under the headings of fundamental themes, main themes, niche themes, and emerging-declining themes. In the fundamental themes section, the concepts of growth, sustainable development, and bibliometric analysis stand out. The concepts of sustainability, policy, governance, science, performance, and education stand out in the main themes section. These concepts guide the literature. The concepts of challenges, security, artificial intelligence, impact, management, and impact are included in the emerging or declining themes section. The niche themes section, which indicates the emergence of specific areas related to inclusive growth, includes the concepts of agriculture, conservation, and food.

4. CONCLUSION

This study, conducted to examine research on inclusive growth, analysed 626 articles published up to January 2026 in the Web of Science (WoS) database. The analysis revealed that the annual growth rate in the field of inclusive growth was 44.62%. In studies on inclusive growth, in which a

total of 2,746 authors conducted academic work, the average number of citations per article was found to be 22.47. The fact that economic growth alone does not determine a country's level of development and that the importance of inclusive growth has been recognised emphasises the significance of this study. This reality indicates that studies in the field of inclusive growth will continue to increase each year.

An analysis of articles on inclusive growth reveals that the university with the highest number of publications in this field is Tamil Nadu Agricultural University with 23 articles, the journal with the most articles is Sustainability with 23 articles, the country with the highest number of articles is the United States with 118 articles, In the geographical analysis of the most cited publications, the United States ranks first with 8,885 citations, and according to the numerical data of the country-ship interaction analysis, the United States ranks first with Freq=495. The findings obtained in the section of the study analysing concept-theme relationships revealed that the words growth, impact, sustainability, management, and sustainable development were predominantly used in studies on inclusive growth. It was determined that concepts such as policy, poverty, climate change, artificial intelligence,

sustainability, and innovation came to the fore in recent trends in studies on inclusive growth. The final part of the analysis, which identified concept-theme relationships, presented findings on the thematic evolution of the concept of inclusive growth. These findings show that sustainability, policy, governance, science, performance, and education concepts stand out in the motor themes section; challenges, security, artificial intelligence, impact, management, and impact concepts are included in the developing or declining themes section; agriculture, conservation, and food concepts are included in the niche themes section; and growth, sustainable development, and bibliometric analysis concepts stand out in the basic themes section.

This study is based on solid foundations in terms of the selected database, the data set used, and the

chosen analysis method. However, this study also has some limitations. The study's limitations include examining only articles, evaluating only articles written in English, and including only studies found in the Web of Science (WoS) database. Therefore, using a data set that includes books, book chapters, and conference papers in addition to articles, studies written in languages other than English, and databases other than Web of Science (WoS) will broaden the scope of future studies. This expansion of the research scope will provide more data on the inclusive growth literature. Finally, it should be noted that the increase in studies brought about by the annual growth rate of the inclusive growth literature will constitute an important source of insight into this field for both future researchers and policymakers.

Author Contributions: For research articles with several authors, a short paragraph specifying them individual contributions must be provided. The following statements should be used "Conceptualization, B.K.A. and B.K.A.; methodology, B. KA.; software, B. KA.; validation, B. KA., B.K.A. and B.K.A.; formal analysis, B.K.A.; investigation, B.K.A.; resources, B.K.A.; data curation, B.K.A.; writing—original draft preparation, B.K.A.; writing—review and editing, B.K.A.; visualization, B.K.A.; supervision, B.K.A.; project administration, B.K.A.; funding acquisition, B.K.A. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript."

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